

Design of Brain Tumor Identification System Using Data Science

¹Ganesh Khekare, ²Patel Yashkumar, ³Patel Nishit, ⁴Prajapati Badal, ⁵Darsh Engineer

^{1,2,3,4,5}Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
^{1,2,3,4,5}Parul Institute of Technology, Parul University, Vadodara, India

Abstract : Brain tumor causes due to rapid growth of cells in uncontrolled manner. It should be treated in earlier stage otherwise it may cause a death of a patient. Accurate detection is one of the key challenges in this field. Many efforts have been made for this but yet something concrete is not achieved. Main challenge is that brain tumor occurs in various shapes, sizes and occur at various location. Our aim is to present a reliable research work and techniques for the brain tumor detection at early stage by using magnetic resonance imaging. Publicly available datasets of MRI images is used to carry out this research work. Data science classification techniques and deep learning techniques are used to predict about the brain tumor. The existing literature is reviewed for the detection of brain tumor and critically analyzed the methods to make scope for the future research.

IndexTerms - Brain tumor, MRI, Brain Tumor Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most common brain deceases is brain tumor. Which is considered as one of the most affected deceases in the modern world which causes many deaths. Many efforts made in this field for early detection of the brain tumor which is helpful for the prevention or curing this deadly decease at earlier stage to save human lives [1]. To counter this problem researchers are trying to adopt new techniques or modifying existing techniques to detect brain tumor at earlier stage accurately and with the high efficiency.

There are mainly two types of brain tumors Primary brain tumor which is also called benign tumor and secondary brain tumor which is also called a malignant tumor. The benign tumor is considered as slow growing cell in the brain. Origin of these brain cells is astrocytes which is non - neuronal brain cells [2]. Primary tumors are less dangerous, but it may result in the secondary tumor at later stage. The secondary tumors are considered as more dangerous, and it spreads aggressively into other tissues. This type of tumor is having a cancer cell which spread into different areas of the brain it is considered as highly malignant [3].

In the year 1969 Raymond v. Damadian invented the first magnetic image. Due to this invention of MRI doctors are able to view the structure of a brain and from those MRI images they are able to study various types of tissues of human brain. Various MRI images can be used for mapping tumor are T1 weighted, T2 weighted and FLAIR which is Fluid attenuated inversion recovery weighted [4]. Brain tumor segmentation is the process of separating the tumor from normal brain tissues; in clinical routine, it provides useful information for diagnosis and treatment planning. However, it is still a challenging task due to the irregular form and confusing boundaries of tumors. Brain tumors will impair IQ, VIQ, and PIQ. The extracerebral tumor resection can deteriorate IQ and PIQ. However, right intracerebral tumor resection is beneficial to VIQ, and transsphenoidal pituitary adenoma resection performs no effect on intelligence. A brain tumor, known as an intracranial tumor, is an abnormal mass of tissue in which cells grow and multiply uncontrollably, seemingly unchecked by the mechanisms that control normal cells. A thin needle is then inserted through the hole. Tissue is removed using the needle, which is frequently guided by CT or MRI scanning. The biopsy sample is then viewed under a microscope to determine if it's cancerous or benign. The outlook for a malignant brain tumour depends on things like where it is in the brain, its size, and what grade it is. It can sometimes be cured if caught early on, but a brain tumour often comes back and sometimes it isn't possible to remove it. The only known environmental cause of brain tumors is having exposure to large amounts of radiation from X-rays or previous cancer treatment. Some brain tumors occur when hereditary conditions are passed down among family members.

Figure 1: T1, T2 Weighted & Flair

The difference between T1 weighted and T2 weighted is that T1 weighted has only one tissue type while T2 weighted has two tissue types which are very bright as shown in figure 1.

II. DATASET

In the deep learning and machine learning methods it is necessary to rely on the large dataset availability. The accuracy of the result depends on the quality of the dataset used for training purpose of the system [5]. We are going to use Kaggle brain tumor dataset for this purpose. It has a separate dataset for images with positive data tumor and negative data tumor so we can train the system for both respectively as shown in figure 2 [6].

Figure 2: Sample Dataset

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is always important for researchers to go through the existing literature before proposing techniques for any specific field. Literature review is used to critically analyses the existing literature and find out the limitations if exist and proposed new techniques or methods to be followed in proposed system [7]. Study by Harlick and Shapiro (1985) shows that purpose of segmentation method is to convert image data available into useful part by separating damaged part and healthy part from the image. Segmentation can be of three types Split and Merge, Clustering and required region growing. Clustering and segmentation both together can be used apply spatial clustering method, result when combine with the histogram techniques gives better results to analyses the final image for the brain tumor detection [8].

As per the study done by J. Zhou (2005), support vector machine (SVM) is used to automate the process of brain tumor segmentation. Advantage of SVM is that it generates very high value dimensional feature vectors. In such a way it produces a required boundary to be considered for decision making process for the tumor region detection [9]. In this technique, sample of image with the tumor should be provided to the SVM classifier while doing process of segmentation. Segmentation of the tumor will be achieved by analysis of this region. Problem with this method is that this method needs to train frequently so it requires interaction of human quite often as per the new images available with the brain tumor dataset [10].

MLP in brain tumor detection is one of the old methods used in the research of Ozkan and Mehmed [11] in this study they initially provide training by the neural network's techniques. Then machine learning model is created from the data prepared by the above training process. Information from next dataset image is used to generate another training records set. The process is repeated for the whole dataset and all the images are changed into segmented iteratively. Detection accuracy of tumor can be measured by the algorithm of Jaccard's similarity in this study. Problem with this algorithm is that it needs interaction from the user, and it is reliable on accuracy of dataset only. Dataset should be updated frequently in order to get proper detection [12].

MLP in detection of brain tumor also possible using textural processing features this approach was used by Kadam D. B. [13], in which contrast, inverse, sum variance and difference entropy was used. In this method monitored training is achieved by training dataset and labeled each image for the positive or negative tumor detection. In the model designed by Kuo-Sheng [14] Hopfield neural network was used in their research, this HNN is capable of segmenting normal brain tissues into anatomical parts very effectively. This updated algorithm of HNN was having an efficiency which is considered as very high. For the brain tumor detection most of the existing system are using image processing techniques very few techniques are available in the case of Machine Learning approach. Machine learning approaches are used by MRI dataset of positive brain tumor dataset only in the existing system [15]. In the image processing techniques CT scan image is captured and by the pre-processing methods this image is segmented. These approaches it is possible to get faulty results. To avoid these more accurate training datasets can be used.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In our proposed system of brain tumor detection includes following basic detection tasks preparing dataset with images with brain and tumor and without brain tumors. Then processing both the dataset as a training dataset. On the basis of training of both the datasets segmentation will be done. At a later stage, we classify the area based on this machine learning approach with splitting of training and testing dataset. As our MRI dataset have preprocessed images this preprocessed image is act as a dataset. At last, we classify the image based on the extracted features by machine learning process.

In this project, we described our goal as the detection of a brain tumor, that is, the presence of a tumor on the provided MRI. The input images will go through following stages as shown in the figure 3.

In the step-in brain tumor detection, we will take the input of the MRI image from the dataset. The MRI images will be preprocessed, and dataset will be used for training for machine learning and deep learning process. The aim of training using dataset is to make further processing fast and accurate. Image segmentation is the process of dividing a digital image into multiple segments that will be helpful in further Processes. In the feature extraction, all the features from the input images will be extracted and then those features will be compared with the trained data set. Finally, after comparing with the trained data set the output will display a message whether the brain tumor is present or not.

Convolution is the next step of CNN in which the feature extraction is performed on the input image. Convolution is a linear operation as the images are often nonlinear, so ReLU layer is used to increase disconnection in the network. In CNN, characteristics are evolved by the preprocessed image using the convolutional and pooling layers. Convolutional Neural Network is a multilevel neural network proficient in identifying visual patterns through learning mechanisms. CNN specifies that the network implies a mathematical operation called convolution. Convolutional Neural networks are limited, which utilize convolution in one of the multiple layers of the network rather than the widely known multiplication matrix. CNN uses fewer parameters and connections than the conventional feedforward neural networks, making the training easier. Feature extraction and detection in CNN are not spatially dependent, and higher-level features are acquired as the input travels to the deeper layers.

Quick and timely recognition of a brain tumor is of the utmost importance for curing the tumor. It depends on the expertise and professional skills of the doctor and which method is selected to treat the patient for rapid recovery. It is challenging to determine the correct type of brain tumor in the initial phase, yet vital as it helps the physicians treat the patient accordingly. Gastrointestinal is the most diagnosed type of cancer. It activates the gastrointestinal polyps. The method of diagnosis of gastrointestinal polyps is video endoscopy. A small camera enters the human body and is guided by the gastrointestinal tract to reveal and exclude polyps. However, some polyps are considered undetected and may be malignant tumors at some point. To reduce the polyp misdetection rate, “a computer-aided polyp detection system” should be used.

Figure 3: Process of Brain Tumor Detection

IV. Result and Conclusion

A method to segment MRI images of the brain to identify the brain tumor using machine learning and deep learning approach is implemented. This system trains the dataset of the MRI images which are having tumors and even do not have any tumor with possible maximum precision. A method which automated the procedure for diagnosing a brain tumor using data science is adopted. Yet there is no perfect method including image processing and MLP through which detection of the brain tumor can be automatically done. Though we can achieve good result using machine learning if proper dataset is available. Our system may have accuracy in the range of 90%- 97%. However, unwanted behavior of the dataset is not taken into consideration so MRI images dataset should be accurate to achieve accurate results for the brain tumor detection. The possibility of future research is also available by selecting proper and more accurate dataset or modifying existing dataset by adding more images and train the system for modified dataset in the future. Figure 4 shows the result of Training Accuracy Vs. Validation Accuracy. Minor difference is there between both the lines, but that minor difference can make a huge impact. Blue lines in graph shows training accuracy, whereas orange lines show validation accuracy.

Figure 4: Training Accuracy Vs. Validation Accuracy

Although the great advance in the field of the brain tumor detection process using machine learning and deep learning methods the robustness factor of this techniques are still a great hurdle for the expert performance of the system and accurate dataset and manual supervision is recommended for accurate detection.

REFERENCES

- [1] Haralick, R.M., and Shapiro, L.G. "SURVEY: image segmentation techniques", Computer Vision Graphics Image Processing, 1985, 29, pp. 100-132.
- [2] J. Zhou, K. L. Chan, V. F. H. Chong and S. M. Krishnan, Extraction of Brain Tumor from MR Images Using One-Class Support Vector Machine, Proceedings of the 2005 IEEE: Engineering in Medicine and Biology 27th annual conference, Shanghai- China, 1-4 Sep. 2005
- [3] Kishore K. Reddy, et al, Confidence Guided Enhancing Brain Tumor Segmentation in Multi-Parametric MRI, 9th IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging, May 2012, pp. 366-369.
- [4] Sonka, M., Hlavac, V., and Boyle, R., "Image Processing, Analysis, and Machine Vision", Brooks / Cole Publishing Company, 1998.
- [5] M. Karnan, diagnose brain tumor through MRI using image processing clustering algorithms such as Fuzzy C Means along with intelligent optimization techniques. In IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICIC), Dec 2010.
- [6] M. F. Othman and M. A. M. Basri, Probabilistic neural network for brain tumor classification. In Second International Conference on Intelligent System, Modelling and Simulation, 2011 Second Edition.
- [7] Abhinav Nagpal, Goldie Gabrani, Python for Data Analytics, Scientific and Technical Application in Amity International Conference for Artificial Intelligence (AICAI), 2019.

- [8] Khekare, G. S. (2014). Design of emergency system for intelligent traffic system using VANET. International Conference on Information Communication and Embedded Systems (ICICES2014), 1-7. doi:10.1109/ICICES.2014.7033910
- [9] S.P. Gohane, G.S. Khekare, Reconfiguration of industrial embedded system in WSN, in 2015 IEEE 9th International Conference on Intelligent Systems and Control (ISCO), Coimbatore, 2015, p. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCO.2015.7282284>.
- [10] Muhmmad Irfan Sharif, Jian Ping Li, Muhammad Attique Khan, Muhammad Asim Saleem, Active Deep neural Network Features Selection for Segmentation and Recognition of Brain Tumors using MRI Images, Pattern Recognition Letters,2019.
- [11] Ozkan, Mehmed, Benoit M. Dawant, and Robert J. Maciunas. "Neural-network-based segmentation of multi-modal medical images: a comparative and prospective study." Medical Imaging, IEEE Transactions on 12.3 (1993).
- [12] Suvidh P Gohane., et al. "Design and Development of New Architecture for Reconfiguration and Processing of Automation Industrial Control System". International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research 6.4 (2015): 1293-1299.
- [13] S.U. Aswathy, Dr G. Glan Deva Dhas, Dr. S.S. Kumar, A Survey on Detection of Brain Tumor from MRI Brain Images, International Conference on Control, Instrumentation, Communication and Computational Technologies (ICCICCT), 2014.
- [14] Ahmed Kharrat, Nacéra Benamrane, Mohamed Ben Messaoud, Mohamed Abid, Detection of Brain Tumor in Medical Images, International Conference on Signals, Circuits and Systems, 2009.
- [15] Parveen, Amritpal Singh, Detection of Brain Tumor in MRI Images, using Combination of Fuzzy C-Means and SVM, International Conference on Signal Processing and Integrated Networks (SPIN),2nd Edition, 2015.